

METHODOLOGY FOR PHASED DEVELOPMENT OF FOOTBALL PLAYERS' TECHNICAL PREPARATION

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ABSTRACT

This work highlights the theoretical foundations and practical aspects of the methodology for the step-by-step development of football players' technical training. In the formation of technical skills, age-related characteristics, the principles of systematicity, consistency, and individualization of training were considered as important factors. The research results demonstrated that the phased development of technical preparation plays a crucial role in enhancing the performance of football players.

Relevance. Modern football is characterized by high speed, precision, and complex technical movements. A footballer's success largely depends on their level of technical proficiency. Technical preparation is a player's skills in handling the ball, as well as their ability to effectively execute movements such as passing, receiving, dribbling, and striking. For the effective development of technical training, it is necessary to organize it in stages. This approach allows for the planning of training sessions in accordance with the player's age, level of preparation, and individual characteristics.

Physical development is one of the most important pillars for a footballer to sustain optimal performance over time. Ximo, head of the physical preparation department at SIA Academy, highlights the importance of respecting the body's natural growth and adaptation pace at each stage:

"Each age has very specific physical characteristics that we must respect and enhance. In the early stages, the goal is general motor development, coordination, and basic endurance. Later, when the body begins to mature, we progressively and carefully introduce strength, speed, and power work to avoid injuries."

This reflection emphasizes the need for a differentiated physical program that does not treat all players equally but adapts to their evolutionary needs and maturational state. At SIA Academy, physical development is divided into three major stages:

Childhood stage (6-10 years): In this initial stage, the aim is to stimulate global motor development through exercises that promote coordination, balance, agility, and light aerobic endurance. Training sessions are playful and varied to create a broad and healthy motor base. The physical load is low to respect natural growth and avoid wear and tear.

Cadet stage (11-14 years): Here, a greater physical load is introduced, with exercises that improve aerobic endurance, flexibility, and an initial strength base, always respecting

bone and muscular development. The work becomes more structured but without losing attention to the body's natural progression.

Youth stage (15-18 years): At this phase, players can train with greater intensity and volume. Specific training is implemented to increase strength, speed, power, and anaerobic endurance. Personalized monitoring is key, since maturation varies among players, and the program must be adjusted to maximize performance and prevent injuries.

Ximo adds emphatically: "At SIA Academy, we have very strict protocols for injury prevention and recovery. We know that proper physical development is the foundation for a player to perform at their highest level throughout their career."

Las etapas del desarrollo físico y técnico por edades en el fútbol.

Each training session in the gym is personalized based on each player's individual conditions.

Technical development: progression and fundamentals

Parallel to physical development, technique is the foundation that supports football performance. Rafa, head of the sports department, explains the importance of working on technique progressively and adapted to each player's stage:

"Technique is a continuous process that must go from simple to complex, always adapted to the player's maturational level. From day one, we work with the basics of control, passing, and shooting, and then we incorporate tactics and real game situations."

Technical training at SIA Academy is also structured by age:

Childhood stage (6-10 years): At this phase, the focus is on ball mastery, eye-foot coordination, and basic fundamentals like short passes and reception. It is essential that children enjoy the game and learn to interact with the ball without pressure. Training fosters creativity and confidence.

Cadet stage (11-14 years): Individual technique is perfected, and basic tactical work begins. Players start working on variations in passing, dribbling, and shooting, as well as principles of collective play. Technical movements under different game circumstances are reinforced.

Youth stage (15-18 years): Technical work is advanced, incorporating complex situations requiring quick and precise decision-making. Emphasis is placed on play in small spaces, adaptability to different positions, and execution under pressure, seeking technical and tactical excellence.

Rafa clearly states: "At the academy, we seek for the player to be capable of executing techniques with precision under pressure. Technical quality, combined with tactical knowledge, is what makes the difference at high performance."

The stages of physical and technical development by age in football.

Technical development is worked on so that all teams achieve strong individual performance.

Integration and coordination at SIA Academy: the value of multidisciplinary work

What really makes SIA Academy special is the harmonious integration between physical and technical aspects in the player's development. The coordination between Ximo and Rafa ensures that training is balanced and adapted to individual needs.

For example, after a technical session with Rafa, players perform specific physical work with Ximo that strengthens the muscular capacities, endurance, or agility necessary to effectively apply the technical skills on the field. This combination is key for performance to be optimal and sustainable. [5, p. 246].

Additionally, the academy carries out continuous and detailed monitoring of each player to adjust loads, intensities, and content, taking into account variables such as physical condition, biological maturation, and technical progress.

This approach guarantees that footballers not only improve their immediate performance but also build a prepared body and refined technique that will accompany them throughout their professional career.

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